

PRE-SERVICE SPECIAL TEACHER EDUCATION THROUGH UNIVERSAL DESIGN FOR LEARNING: TRANSFORMING INCLUSIVE PRACTICES IN SCHOOL EDUCATION

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Paper Received On: 20 JANUARY 2026

Peer Reviewed On: 24 FEBRUARY 2026

Published On: 01 MARCH 2026

Abstract

This paper explores the integration of Universal Design for Learning (UDL) within Special Teacher Education programmes from a transformative perspective. It argues for a shift in teacher preparation towards approaches that are more equitable, design-focused, and responsive to the diverse needs of learners. Drawing on recent research, the paper reflects on the limitations of conventional teacher education models and highlights how UDL can support more inclusive and flexible pedagogical practices. The paper sets out clear objectives, outlines an appropriate methodological approach, and proposes a theoretical model aimed at strengthening teacher preparation for inclusive classrooms. Traditionally, Special Teacher Education has focused on helping teachers respond to learning difficulties after they arise. Such practices often rely on deficit-based thinking and tend to address learner differences in a fragmented way, which limits the development of truly inclusive teaching strategies. It encourages teachers to design learning experiences that are flexible and accessible for all students, rather than making adjustments later. By incorporating UDL into teacher education programmes, this paper emphasizes the importance of moving from reactive teaching approaches to more proactive and thoughtful instructional design.

Keywords: *Universal Design for Learning, Special Teacher Education, Inclusion, Transformative Pedagogy, Educational Innovation*

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Introduction

Special Teacher Education has evolved along with broader social movements ensuring that children with special educational needs are afforded their right to quality learning opportunities. Earlier from the behaviourist and medical perspectives, disability was conceptualized as a deficit model which needs accommodation and modification (Kauffman & Hallahan, 2011). The responsibility for change was placed on the learner, while educational systems emphasized processes of assessment, classification, and treatment.

Research indicates that the teachers remain inadequately prepared to respond to the dynamic and increasingly diverse conditions of classrooms, where the teaching learning practices rely on rigid, one-size-fits-all approaches rather than flexible, design-oriented principles (Florian & Black-Hawkins, 2011; Sharma, Loreman, & Forlin, 2012). This highlights a gap between inclusive education policies and its implementation.

In this context, Universal Design for Learning (UDL) brings a shift by reorienting traditional assumptions about teaching and learning. Without emphasizing learner deficits UDL advocates for design of curriculum, pedagogy, and assessment. In this framework, learner diversity is placed as the foundation of educational planning. UDL emphasizes on creating flexible learning environments to incorporate multiple means of engagement, representation, and expression, to ensure equitable access to learning for all students (Rose & Meyer, 2002; Meyer, Rose, & Gordon, 2014).

In this context, the paper aims:

- to examine and develop a theoretical framework for integrating UDL principles into Pre-service Special Teacher Education programmes, with a focus on strengthening inclusive pedagogical design.
- identify the core competencies and skills required by special education teachers to create inclusive, flexible, and effective learning environments.

Method: The paper was written through analysis of secondary data. A wide range of research studies, policy documents, theoretical literature, and scholarly reports related to UDL and Special Teacher Education were reviewed and analysed. By analysing these diverse sources, the paper aims to generate new perspectives and propose a conceptual framework for the preparation of special education teachers.

Concept of Special Teacher Education

Special Teacher Education refers to the systematic preparation and professional development of teachers to work effectively for the learners with diverse abilities, including those with

disabilities, learning difficulties, and exceptional talents (Kauffman & Hallahan, 2011; Florian, 2014). It includes specialized training aimed at equipping teachers with the knowledge, skills, attitudes, and updated pedagogical competencies required to address the varied needs of learners in an inclusive educational setting (Sharma, Loreman, & Forlin, 2012).

It stresses on understanding of different categories of disabilities and learning differences, along with the adaptation of curriculum, pedagogical strategies, and assessment practices to ensure meaningful participation of all learners in the classroom (Friend & Bursuck, 2019). It also provides platform for effective integration of assistive technologies and inclusive teaching learning practices to support cognitive, social, and emotional development of learners (Rose & Meyer, 2002).

Teachers are trained to work in partnership with community - parents, caregivers, therapists, and other professionals to create supportive and holistic learning environments (Florian & Black-Hawkins, 2011) to enhance the effectiveness of interventions. Special Teacher Education is increasingly aligned with inclusive and design-based frameworks, moving beyond deficit-oriented models towards valuing learner diversity for enriching teaching and learning processes (Florian, 2014; Forlin, 2010). It was also criticised for its limited emphasis on universal practices and design-oriented pedagogy for the benefit of all learners (Florian & Rouse, 2009; Smith & Tyler, 2011).

Transformative perspectives advocate a dynamic interaction between the learner and multiple contextual factors, including the environment, curriculum design, and social relationships (Bronfenbrenner, 1979; Slee, 2011). Accordingly, it creates a base for this shift of the teacher from a practitioner focused on intervention and remediation to a designer of inclusive learning environments.

Universal Design for Learning (UDL)

Universal Design for Learning (UDL) emerged as a response to the limitations inherent in standardized and one-size-fits-all approaches to teaching and learning. It is an educational framework aims to make learning accessible, flexible, and engaging for all learners through new deliberate design of curriculum, pedagogy, and assessment (CAST, 2018). UDL emphasizes the provision of multiple means of representation, engagement, and expression to accommodate this variability (Rose & Meyer, 2002; Meyer, Rose, & Gordon, 2014). By incorporating diverse instructional methods, media, and assessment strategies, UDL aims to minimize barriers to learning and maximize opportunities for participation and success among

learners with varied abilities. UDL promotes proactive design fostering inclusive and equitable learning environments (CAST, 2018).

UDL has interdisciplinary foundations, including cognitive neuroscience, constructivist learning theory, and equity-oriented perspectives of education (Rose & Meyer, 2002; Meyer et al., 2014). This framework is supported by three interconnected brain networks: the affective network (related to motivation and engagement), the recognition network (involved in perception and comprehension of information), and the strategic network (associated with planning and performing tasks) (Rose & Meyer, 2002).

In the context of Special Teacher Education, it represents a shift approach that changes role of the teacher-from an interventionist addressing deficits to a designer of inclusive learning environments through instructional planning, reflective practice, and a commitment to systemic equity in education (Florian & Black-Hawkins, 2011; Mezirow, 1997). Its effective implementation depends on several critical factors, including teacher preparedness, institutional support, and alignment with culturally focused pedagogies (Paris & Alim, 2017; Hitchcock et al., 2002). This approach aligns with contemporary pedagogical innovation that benefits all learners across linguistic, cultural, cognitive, and physical dimensions (Kurth & Mastergeorge, 2012; Smith, 2014).

When applied within teacher preparation programmes, UDL equips educators with the competencies to design pedagogy to make:

- flexible learning objectives accommodating diverse learner needs.
- multiple means of representation, enabling learners to access various modalities.
- multiple means of expression, allowing students to demonstrate diverse forms of assessment and performance.

Understanding a Transformative Approach

Transformation in teacher education extends beyond the development of competencies and skills, rather involves a shift in thinking, reflection, and engagement with professional practice (Mezirow, 1997; Cranton, 2006). The concept of perspective transformation entails educators' assumptions about learners, diversity, and nature of teaching (Taylor, 2008). In this context, Special Teacher Education, requires a movement from deficit-oriented, learner-fixing approaches towards redesigning learning environments for inclusive platform.

A transformative approach for UDL emphasizes development of reflective, critical, and equity-oriented practitioners encompassing-

- beliefs and assumptions on ability, disability, and diversity.

- design-oriented thinking in teaching learning planning.
- pedagogical practices to address systemic and structural barriers to learning.
- Engaging students, families, and professional peers in creating inclusive learning environment.

This perspective allows advocating adaptive, participatory, and social justice-oriented teacher education (Zeichner, 2010; Sapon-Shevin, 2017). It shifts teacher education from a technical endeavour to a transformative process for preparing educators as reflective practitioners and change agents in inclusive education.

Landscape of Pre-Service Special Teacher Education and UDL

Inclusive education has received significant attention at the global level, particularly through policy initiatives that emphasise equity and access for all learners. Despite these developments, the integration of UDL into Special Teacher Education programmes continues to be limited.

Studies suggest that many pre-service teachers are introduced to UDL in a limited or fragmented manner during their training. As a result, their understanding of inclusive pedagogical design remains partial, which affects application of such approaches effectively in classrooms (Smith & Lowrey, 2016; McGhie-Richmond et al., 2016).

Preparing future teachers needs training on UDL to integrate into practice (Hitchcock et al., 2002). In practice, the use of UDL is limited to specific classrooms rather than being integrated across entire programmes (Rao & Meo, 2016). In addition, institutional challenges such as curricula, resources, and resistance to new pedagogical approaches can play a vital role in adopting. Therefore, there is a clear need to embed UDL more systematically in Special Teacher Education. This may involve revisiting curriculum structures, enhancing the capacity of teacher educators, and aligning institutional practices with inclusive principles.

Special Teacher Education through Universal Design for Learning (UDL)

Shifting from Remediation to Design-Oriented Pedagogy: Traditional approaches to Special Teacher Education are based on remediation and individualized adaptations supporting learners with disabilities (Kauffman & Hallahan, 2011). In contrast, the UDL promotes a proactive and design-oriented approach to pedagogy, in place of focusing on remediation. It advocates for the development of curriculum, pedagogy, and assessment that are inherently flexible and accessible (CAST, 2018; Rose & Meyer, 2002). It reframes learner variability as a natural and expected characteristic of all classrooms. UDL shifts the focus from “fixing” the learner to designing inclusive learning environments, it encourages educators to anticipate diversity and

minimize potential barriers beforehand. This approach enhances accessibility and improves learning opportunities for learners with disabilities.

Transformative Teacher Preparation: Reframing Special Teacher Education through UDL requires a shift in how teachers are prepared for practice. Instead of focusing only on techniques and strategies, a transformative approach encourages the educators to critically examine their assumptions about learners, diversity, and inclusion (Mezirow, 1997; Florian & Black-Hawkins, 2011). Teacher preparation, therefore, becomes a process of developing reflective practitioners who can design inclusive learning environments. It involves engaging with flexible teaching approaches, understanding cultural and linguistic diversity, and acknowledging neurodiversity. Collaboration with stakeholders- students, families, and peers becomes central to co-construct meaningful learning experiences.

Integration of UDL in Special Teacher Education Curricula: For effective integration of UDL, it must be embedded throughout teacher education programmes. It means integrating UDL principles across all courses and ensuring that they update theoretical and practical aspects of training. Teacher trainees should be provided with opportunities to design, implement, and evaluate flexible lesson plans in real classroom contexts. In addition, assessment practices need to reflect UDL principles by allowing multiple ways for learners to demonstrate their understanding and by promoting learner autonomy (Rao, Ok, & Bryant, 2014).

Development of Teacher Competencies for Inclusive Practice: The inclusion of UDL in Special Teacher Education contributes to the development of key professional competencies. Teachers learn to accommodate diverse learning needs and to design lessons to meet a wide range of learners. This also includes developing an awareness of equity and access. Reflective practice encourages teachers to evaluate and refine their pedagogical approaches. These competencies support inclusive and responsive learning environments.

Implementing UDL in Special Teacher Education

The concept of UDL embodies in policies and frameworks through its vision of inclusive, flexible, and learner-centred education. The integration of UDL is conceptualised through inclusive education in Special Teacher Education in the National Education Policy (NEP, 2020) and the National Curriculum Framework for School Education (NCFSE, 2023). Both documents emphasize inclusivity, equity, flexibility, and learner-centered pedagogy, thereby creating a conducive environment as a foundational approach in teacher preparation.

Curriculum Transformation in Alignment with NEP 2020 and NCFSE 2023: NEP 2020 and NCFSE 2023 advocate flexible, multidisciplinary, and competency-based curricula, with experiential, inclusive, and context-sensitive learning. The policy provides a strong basis for integrating UDL into Special Teacher Education curricula. Teacher education programmes can operationalize policy mandates and move toward design-oriented pedagogical frameworks embedding the principles of accessibility, flexibility, and learner variability across all courses.

Enhancing Teacher Preparedness: NEP 2020 and NCFSE 2023 emphasize the importance of continuous professional development and reflective practice among teachers. Structured training programmes, practice-based learning experiences, and reflective engagement support in translating inclusive policy visions into classroom realities in bridging the gap between theoretical and pedagogical practice. This provides a strong basis for improving teachers' capacity to adopt design-based learning, i.e., UDL in diverse classroom settings.

Institutional Culture and Leadership for Inclusive Innovation: NEP 2020 highlights the role of institutional autonomy and leadership in fostering innovation. In implementing the Policy, curriculum framework (NCFSE 2023) emphasises on collaborative and inclusive school cultures, which is a requisite for visualising UDL. Institutions can facilitate the systematic adoption of UDL within teacher education, by participatory decision-making.

Optimization of Digital Resources: NCFSE 2023 encourages the use of diverse learning resources with contextual adaptations. Open educational resources, and assistive technologies are essential to enhance accessibility and inclusivity, even within resource-constrained settings.

Reimagining Assessment Practices: The UDL aligned practices create platform for competency-based, formative, and flexible assessment systems, focusing on holistic and continuous evaluation. The policies and frameworks also provide a foundation for aligning assessment practices with UDL principles. Multiple and flexible modes of assessment, educators can accurately record diverse learner outcomes and promote meaningful engagement.

Conclusion

Universal Design for Learning (UDL) provides a meaningful framework particularly in context of Special Teacher Education programmes for effective inclusive education. The current practices based on behaviourist and medical models are traditional which requires remediation (Kauffman & Hallahan, 2011; Lindsay, 2007). UDL may create a platform for teacher preparation to focus more on proactive and design-oriented pedagogy. As a result, curriculum,

pedagogy and will be flexible and inclusive (Florian & Black-Hawkins, 2011; Sharma, Loreman, & Forlin, 2012).

In this regard, the policy provisions emphasize on learner-centered pedagogy, flexibility, and continuous professional development, encouraging teachers for innovations in instructional models. NCFSE 2023 also spells about importance on institutional culture and processes, highlighting the need for effective schooling, which depends on effective teacher preparation in teacher education institutions. Hence, a collaborative, reflective, and inclusive models will be helpful for this.

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